

pySmooth: Time Series Analysis in Python From First Principles

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

Humans seek to know what the future holds for better planning and organization. Have you considered how to use a combination of financial metrics to track and predict a target metric? Time series analysis can provide a method for estimating the future based on past data.

2. Aim

This talk focuses on time series analysis from first principles. We would cover topics ranging from time difference model, ARIMA model, and Kalman filtering model by providing barebone implementation in Python for each models. We will place emphasis in Kalman filtering models.

A number of kalman filtering solution has been biased towards location-based problems. This talk aims to change that stereotype by describing kalman filtering in a form suited for time series analysis and other kinds of applications.

Kalman filtering is an estimation technique that is suited for time series analysis (filtering, forecasting), sensor fusion, and localization. This can be used as a basis for converting static models into incremental learning models.

Kalman filtering works using a two-step process of prediction and correction under some conditions can ensure that we can have a self-correcting system as sample size increases.

The plan for the talk with time estimation in each section is shown below. I will present my new time series library that mirrors the content of the talk named PySmooth (<https://github.com/kenluck2001/pySmooth>).

3. Material and methods

Notes

This talk code made use of multivariate time series for internal code examples. It should generalize to the univariate cases also. Furthermore, I will present a new time series library that mirrors the content of the talk that will be named PySmooth. The author of the library is the same as the speaker for the talk.

This is a tentative plan for the slides.

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Introduction [3 minutes]

Brief Bio

Motivate the problem

Time difference model [4 minutes]

Present mathematical formulation.

Discuss the limitations and benefits.

Provide implementation in Python.

Incremental ARIMA model [5 minutes]

This is a special case of time difference model with unique properties.

Present mathematical formulation.

Discuss the limitations and benefits.

Provide implementation in Python.

Kalman filtering model [15 minutes]

This builds on the preceding sections by allowing for conditioning on some observed measurement. The topics should include:

Recursive linear regression

Discrete Kalman filters

Extended Kalman filters

Unscented Kalman filters

We will provide the following description for each of the topics in this section.

Present mathematical formulation.

Discuss the limitations and benefits.

Provide implementation in Python.

Evaluation [3 minutes]

Use Bitcoin time series data for demonstration.

Provide

4. Results

This is aimed at providing a clear explanation of techniques in time series analysis to the audience.

5. Conclusions

A new time series analysis in Python.

6. Keywords

kalman-filter, signal-processing, and time-series-analysis

Author biography

Kenneth Emeka Odoh Kenneth is a polyglot, who is regular contributor at a number of (data science / machine learning / Python) meet ups in the Vancouver area. As a graduate student, I did research in the field of visual analytic at the University of Regina where I had worked on a number of industrial sponsored visualization projects and published a few research papers (<https://scholar.google.ca/citations?user=3G2ncgwAAAAJ&hl=en>). I had worked in a fintech early stage start up remotely in Toronto for political risk prediction using machine learning. This was where I came in contact with multiple ways of doing time series analysis. I have reviewed two software development textbooks at Packt publishing, 2015. At the moment, I am working in a start up in Vancouver as a software engineer for voip and IOT related projects.

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